

The Role of Security Agencies in Curbing Violent Crimes in Nigeria: A Study of Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

The study investigated the role of security agencies in curbing violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Uyo and Itu Local Government Areas were the study area. Descriptive survey research design and historical research design were adopted in the study. Questionnaire was designed in both structured and unstructured formats for collection of quantitative data. In addition, In-depth Interview (IDI) guide was used for collection of qualitative data among opinion leaders and security personnel. Secondary data were gathered from newspaper and online news. Four hundred (400) respondents were sampled purposively. Population of the study comprises security personnel, opinion and community leaders from the age cohorts of 18 years and above. Out of 400 copies of questionnaire distributed, only 395 were returned and same were used for statistical analysis. Quantitative data collected were statistically presented and analyzed using frequency tables and simple percentages. Qualitative data were presented and analyzed using conversational analysis method. Findings revealed that routine patrols, tip-off, stop and search, checkpoints/roadblock, arrest and detentions and other strategies currently used by security agencies are not enough to deter or reduce the rate of violent crimes in the state. In addition, ill-equipped workforce, corruption, poor welfare packages, among others are the major hindrances to effective security architecture in Akwa Ibom State. More so, cultism, aggravated assault, rape, kidnapping, illegal arms, murder, armed robbery are the most occurring violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State. The study recommends that every community should embrace and adopt community watch as a crime prevention method; cooperation and partnerships between the security agencies and citizens are necessary; there is need for government at all levels to ensure a permanent place for crime prevention in their structures and programmes; informants who volunteer information or tip-offs on violent crimes to security agencies should be encouraged and protected.

Keywords: *Role, Security Agencies, Curbing, Violent Crime, Prevention*

Introduction

The apparent escalation of violent crimes in the world is an issue that has been gaining more attention in both developing and developed nations. In 2018, 42 of the world's 50 most violent cities were in Latin America. Four were in United States, with another in Puerto Rico. The region is the world's most violent, excluding war zones, with bloodshed driven by organized crime and

exacerbated by chronic instability, poverty and corruption (Woody, 2019). According to the statistics released by the Nigeria's National Bureau of Statistics (2016) cited in Oguntunde *et al.* (2018), Lagos, Abuja, Delta, Kano, Plateau, Ondo, Oyo, Bauchi, Adamawa and Gombe States made the top ten states in Nigeria with high number of crimes.

Violent crime is a dynamic interaction between an offender and a victim in which coercive force is applied by the offender to subdue the victim by injuring him or her, taking away his or her property, and causing his or her death (Iwarimie-Jaja, 2012). Whatever dimension violent crime takes, its consequences are always harmful to the victim, his/her family, community and the society at large. Iwarimie-Jaja (2012: 257) asserts that:

“Violent crime encapsulates harmful, destructive and injurious acts such as murder, manslaughter, rape, aggravated assault and arson. In any form it takes, it may be sufficient in scope and intensity to threaten and/ or disorganize society. This can result to terror when it involves mass killing, maiming, and destruction of property. There are much daily violent crime activities in all societies, perpetrated by deviant persons who are predatory to criminals” (Iwarimie-Jaja, 2012: 257).

For Iwarimie-Jaja (2012), there is no one alive today, child or adult who has not personally experienced violent crime or had a friend or relative who has not been violently victimized; or has a relative, friend or neighbor robbed, killed, beaten/assaulted, maimed, or property burnt. Violent crimes permeate or affect churches, businesses, homes, automobiles, schools, and everything owned by humans. There is need to control or prevent violent crime and the security agencies like the Nigeria Police Force, Department of State Services, Nigeria Security and Civil Defense Corps, Nigeria Custom Service, Nigeria Drugs Law Enforcement Agency, Nigeria Prison Service, Nigeria Army and Nigeria Immigration Service are saddled directly or indirectly with the responsibility of ensuring maintenance of law and order, which invariably include the protection of lives and property, prevention of crimes and apprehension of offenders. In most cases, these security agencies have adopted various strategies of crime control, including stop and search, tip off, operation/raid, show of force, patrol and tracking system (Etuk, 2018), but in spite of all these, the rate of violent crimes are still on the increase. Evidence from research, however, suggests that these strategies are relatively ineffective in reducing crime and detecting offenders (Karn, 2013 cited in Etuk, 2018). While the Police and other security agencies consistently declare their supremacy over crime and criminals, the phenomenon of crime has continued to increase, with severe consequences to both the individuals and the society (Etuk, 2018).

The high rate of violent crime has created an atmosphere of fear, anxiety and tension (a state of insecurity). Okechukwu (2012) has argued that violent crimes such as murder, armed robbery, kidnapping and terrorism are the most inhumane crimes that continue to plague Nigeria. The recent upsurge in violent crimes in Nigeria has created enormous uncertainty in the security of lives and property of individuals and of social stability in general. The incidents of traditional crimes such as armed robbery, arson, murder, kidnapping, rape, hired assassins and ritual killings are examples of the most serious violent crimes which have been on the increase in the recent past (Brownson, 2012).

The increase in the number of violent crimes reported in Akwa Ibom State, and their serious negative effects to the residents should be wake up call to the law enforcement agencies. Newspaper report in Akwa Ibom State revealed that residents of the state in all the three senatorial districts have resigned to a life of fear, anguish and misery following the unhindered activities of armed robbers in all major cities and villages which made the residents of these cities to become helpless preys to the increasing gangs of armed robbers. These armed robbers seem to have divided themselves into different gangs for the purpose of terrorizing the residents of the city. In fact, there is hardly a day that passes without ten robbery cases happening in different parts of Uyo (The Guide Newspaper Editorial, 2017). Anthony (2018) reported that seven persons have been jailed for rape

in Akwa Ibom State while 30 cases are ongoing in court. In a similar scenario, Onuegbu (2018) reported that four undergraduate students of Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus were suspended by the University authority for allegedly raping a female student.

Despite the core functions of the Nigeria Police Force which are detection and prevention of crime, the police and other law enforcement agencies have not been able to prevent violent crimes to the satisfaction of the public. Expatriates and affluent Nigerians employ their own security, and use armored vehicles for travel. Businesses and individuals frequently hire police officers and other law enforcement agents to provide armed private security. Most businesses employ guard services, and many companies offer varying quality of service. As Nigerian law prohibits the arming of private security personnel, police often supplement guard forces; you can make these arrangements via your local guard company or at a local police station. Therefore, private security companies have responded by providing private security services, with the aim of helping the affected residents to improve their own security. However, this has not been the case as crimes such as robbery; car snatching, cultism, homicide, suicide, child theft, acid bath, murder and rape have continued to thrive even with the heavy presence of the law enforcement agents. Attacks on businesses and individuals have adversely affected business viability and economic and community stability. It is noteworthy that even after some local residents of Akwa Ibom State engaged the services of private security companies to enhance their individual safety, they have continued to experience major violent crime challenges. It seems that the availability of security agencies in the area of study has achieved very little in the control of violent crimes.

It is against this background that the study sought to investigate the role of security agencies in curbing violent crimes in Nigeria, using Akwa Ibom State as a case study. Emphasis was on the strategies adopted by security agencies in the prevention of violent crimes, the hindrances of the security agencies in the course of performing their duties in relation to violent crimes and ascertaining the most prevalent forms of violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State. The following research questions guided the study;

- i. What are the roles of security agencies in curbing violent crimes?
- ii. How effective are the strategies adopted by security agencies in curbing violent crimes?
- iii. What constitute hindrances to curbing violent crimes among security agencies in Akwa Ibom State?
- iv. What is the level and trend of violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State?

What is Violent Crime?

Violent crimes are violations of criminal law that involve the intentional use of violence by one person against another (Rosenfeld, 2017). Adegoke and Usuh (2008:126) defined it as “harmful, destructive and injurious acts which has the capacities to threaten and disorganize a society. This can result when it involves mass killing, maiming and destruction of property”. A violent crime is a crime in which the offender uses or threatens to use violent force upon the victim. Simply put, a violent crime belongs to the class of crimes containing some element of violence. Threats of harm, especially when immediate causes fear, can also be considered violent crimes under specific circumstances. Violent crimes are often set in contrast to other types of crime, such as property crime, because the other party does not get injured.

According to Iwarimie-Jaja (2012), Adegoke and Usuh (2008) different violent crime categories vary based on jurisdiction. However, in general, violent crimes include:

- Assault and/or battery
- Robbery, which can be defined as theft combined with the use of force
- Various types of homicides, including murder and manslaughter
- Kidnapping and Hostage-taking
- Murder and Homicide
- Domestic violence

- Rape
- Cultism
- Terrorism
- Armed robbery.

Violent crimes may be considered a misdemeanor or felony. However, there are some crimes such as homicide that will always be considered a felony crime. Threats of harm may also constitute violent crime status, as long as the victim has a reasonable apprehension that bodily injury will occur (Peeler, 2021). Federal Bureau of Investigation (2011) in their research revealed that the homicide rate is much higher in large cities than in small towns. In 2010, the homicide rate (number of homicides per 100,000 in population) in cities with a population at or over 250,000 was 10.0 percent, compared to only 2.5 percent in towns with a population between 10,000 and 24,999. Homicide, of course, is considered the most serious crime because it involves the taking of a human life. As well, homicide data are considered more accurate than those for other crimes because most homicides come to the attention of the police and are more likely than other crimes to lead to an arrest. For its part, the focus on rape and sexual assault reflects the contemporary women's movement's interest in these related crimes beginning in the 1970s and the corresponding interest of criminologists, both female and male, in the criminal victimization of women.

Rape and sexual assault against women are serious manifestation of gender inequality. According to Heise *et al.* (1999), estimates show that one-third of women on the planet have been raped or sexually assaulted, beaten, or physically abused in some other way. While it is tempting to conclude that such violence is much more common in poor nations than in a wealthy nation like the United States,. Like homicide, about three-fourths of all rapes and sexual assaults involve individuals who know each other, not strangers.

Meaning of Security Agencies

According to Alabi (2020) security agency is a government organization which is responsible for security intelligence activities within a nation. Example of security agencies are the Nigeria Police Force, Military (Army, Navy and Air Force), FRSC (Federal Road Safety Corp), NDLEA (National Drugs Law Enforcement Agency), SSS (State Security Service), ICPC (Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission), NSCDC (Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corp), NCS (Nigeria Correctional Service), Nigeria Customs, NAFDAC (National Agency for Food Drugs Administration and Control), EFCC (Economic and Financial Crimes Commission), etc. Alabi (2020) further added that the primary duties of security agencies include;

- i. Maintenance of law and order in the country
- ii. Protect the country against domestic threats
- iii. Defend the country against internal and external aggression
- iv. Protect lives and property of the citizens
- v. Punish and detain offenders according to the law

What is Crime Prevention?

Prevention is the first imperative to justice. United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2010) defined crime prevention as comprising strategies and measures that seek to reduce the risk of crimes occurring, and their potential harmful effects on individuals and society, including fear of crime, by intervening to influence their multiple causes. Also, Economic and Social Council Resolution (2002) cited in United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2010) observed that well-planned crime prevention strategies not only prevent crime and victimization, but also promote community safety and contribute to sustainable development of countries. Effective, responsible crime prevention enhances the quality of life of all citizens. It has long-term benefits in terms of

reducing the costs associated with the formal criminal justice system, as well as other social costs that result from crime.

The basic principles underlying the Guidelines for the Prevention of Crime

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2010) set out eight basic principles underlying the development of crime prevention strategies in chapter III, as follows:

- i. **Government leadership:** All levels of government should play a leadership role in developing effective and humane crime prevention strategies and in creating and maintaining institutional frameworks for their implementation and review.
- ii. **Socio-economic development and inclusion:** Crime prevention considerations should be integrated into all relevant social and economic policies and programmes, including those addressing employment, education, health, housing and urban planning, poverty, social marginalization and exclusion. Particular emphasis should be placed on communities, families, children and youth at risk.
- iii. **Cooperation/partnerships:** Cooperation/partnerships should be an integral part of effective crime prevention, given the wide-ranging nature of the causes of crime and the skills and responsibilities required to address them. This includes partnerships working across ministries and between authorities, community organizations, non-governmental organizations, the business sector and private citizens.
- iv. **Sustainability/accountability:** Crime prevention requires adequate resources, including funding for structures and activities, in order to be sustained. There should be clear accountability for funding, implementation and evaluation and for the achievement of planned results.
- v. **Knowledge base:** Crime prevention strategies, policies, programmes and actions should be based on a broad, multidisciplinary foundation of knowledge about crime problems, their multiple causes and promising and proven practices.
- vi. **Human rights/rule of law/culture of lawfulness:** The rule of law and those human rights which are recognized in international instruments to which Member States are parties must be respected in all aspects of crime prevention. A culture of lawfulness should be actively promoted in crime prevention.
- vii. **Interdependency:** National crime prevention diagnoses and strategies should, where appropriate, take account of links between local criminal problems and international organized crime.
- viii. **Differentiation:** Crime prevention strategies should, when appropriate, pay due regard to the different needs of men and women and consider the special needs of vulnerable members of society.

Security Agencies and their Strategies in Curbing Violent Crimes

Etuk (2018) posits that one important strategy of violent crime control that has received global recognition is the 'stop and search'. This strategy is also documented by Karn (2013) cited in Etuk (2018) observed that stop and search enables the police to allay or confirm suspicions about individuals and detect those suspected of carrying weapons, stolen goods or being equipped for stealing. The Police argue that the use of stop and search strategy disrupts and deters criminal activity, rather than simply detecting it (The Police Foundation, 2012).

The Police Act in Section 29, states that a police officer '...may detain and search any person whom he reasonably suspects of having in his possession or conveying in any manner anything which he has reason to believe to have been stolen or otherwise unlawfully obtained.' Therefore, the police have the power to search, but it is however, not absolute. There has to be a reasonable suspicion that the person has stolen or unlawfully obtained property in his/her

possession. That is the position of the law. The test to decide what is reasonable is something referred to as the ‘objective test’ i.e. whether a reasonable man would have conducted the search of a person in the circumstances.

Security agencies also make use of ‘tip-off’ strategy to control violent crimes. White (2011) observed that in a civilized society where the rule of law, patriotism, loyalty and good welfare package principles are practiced by both government and citizenry, tip-off has served as a veritable tool for effective control strategy of violent and non-violent crimes. In addition, Karn (2013) cited in Etuk (2018) posits that tip-off can prevent casualties because the security operatives have a pre-information or perhaps, details of the criminal activities, modus operandi, types of weaponry, armory, numerical strength of the criminal gang, their base, or location etc. will be in advantage position to plan ahead of the criminal element therefore, success is inevitable in such situation.

Another strategy common to security agencies is patrol. Patrol is typically the largest function in police agencies around the world, and the majority of officers tend to be assigned to general service duties (Bayley, 1992 cited in Telep *et al.*, 2016). Patrol officers generally spend their time responding to emergency calls for service from the public, deterring crime through their presence, and carrying out special assignments from supervisors. In recent years, it has become increasingly recognized that police agencies can have a beneficial impact on crime and disorder (Lum *et al.*, 2011 cited in Telep *et al.*, 2016). Police patrol officers have likely played a major role in police efforts to effectively address crime as these officers make up a substantial portion of police resources and are on the front lines responding to crime and citizen concerns on a daily basis.

A statement by the Nigeria Police Force spokesman, CSP Jimoh Moshood in Abuja, said that the Inspector General of Police (IGP), Ibrahim Idris directed immediate commencement of stop and search operations across the country to prevent crimes and criminality throughout the yuletide and as well directed all State Police Commands across the country to beef security at flash points, black spots and vulnerable points on major roads and highways across the country. He warned that in order to ensure free flow of traffic and ease movement of travellers, the operation should not be located at areas susceptible to traffic gridlock or vehicular hold-ups (Ikeji, 2017).

We could recall that Frank Mba, Police Spokesman, disclosed the directive of the IGP M. A Adamu on the banned of the personnel of the Federal Special Anti-Robbery Squad (FSARS) and other Tactical Squads of the Force including the Special Tactical Squad (STS), Intelligence Response Team (IRT), Anti-Cultism Squad and other Tactical Squads operating at the Federal, Zonal and Command levels, from carrying out routine patrols and other conventional low-risk duties, stop and search duties, checkpoints, mounting of roadblocks, traffic checks, etc. The directive came in the wake of an outrage over alleged criminal and extra-judicial actions of FSARS officers against citizens in various parts of the country (Shibayan, 2020).

Hindrances to Security Agencies in Curbing Violent Crimes

The government’s ineptitude and laxity in dealing with security challenges has posed a problem for the security forces in discharging their duties. Nigeria’s borders are porous thereby making it possible for infiltration of mercenaries and arms proliferation into the country. Nigerian security forces are finding it difficult to end insecurity in the country. This was evidenced when almost 400 Nigerian Army personnel detailed to fight Boko Haram in Borno State resigned their appointments under the guise of tactical withdrawal. This has been attributed to lack of training and lack of modern fighting equipment. The Nigerian military has admitted that hundreds of government troops fled from heavy fighting with Boko Haram, but said their apparent escape to neighbouring Cameroon was a “tactical manoeuvre” (Nnenah, 2014 cited in Onyepuemu, 2015).

Omotosho and Aderinto (2012) believe that no effort by the Nigeria Police can control crime in society because of inadequacies within the force, especially in terms of manpower, technological advancement and other problems affecting their performance. Such inadequacies have prompted individuals to look elsewhere for their personal safety and security. It is this weakened capacity of

government, and particularly the police, to combat crime and other vices within society that has led to the proliferation of private security firms across Nigeria. It is evidenced from previous studies that some types of economic crimes are beyond the scope and jurisdiction of public law enforcement agencies, because they do not have the sufficient resources, expertise and technological know-how to track sophisticated criminals (Chinwokwu, 2018).

Onovo (2005) stated that the barriers that reduce the capacity of agencies to share criminal intelligence include lack of a national process for generating and sharing intelligence, existence of laws that unduly restrict law enforcement access to information, the hierarchical structures of sharing information, deficits in criminal intelligence analysis, and lack of good technologies to support criminal intelligence sharing. He stated further that in Nigeria, security agencies like the Military, the SSS, Customs, Immigration, NDLEA etc. may talk about their routine sharing of criminal intelligence with the police through the Inspector General of Police or the State Commissioners of Police, and during the monthly Joint Intelligence Board meetings, but the current framework is inadequate. In these days of threat of armed robbery, assassinations and other violent crimes, there is the dire need for a national policy on 'interagency criminal intelligence sharing' a policy that will make it possible and mandatory for the various security agencies to provide unclassified information to the Police Force Headquarters, the Zonal Assistant Inspector General of Police, the State Command Commissioners, the Area Commanders and the Divisional Police Officers on daily basis. The rationale is that such information will help the police to act both proactively to prevent crime as well as reactively to bring criminals to face the law (Kenechukwu, 2012).

Evidence shows that corruption has been one of the hindrances to security agencies in fighting violent crime. Researches in Africa have shown, for example, that corruption had caused security agencies to become ineffective, sometimes predatory (Magahy *et al.*, 2009). At the same time, public distrust can contribute to an environment where citizens perceive corruption to be a more effective recourse for securing their own protection (Transparency International, 2010).

The Nigeria Police Force (2008), in their annual report noted that the police is handicapped because of combination of factors that plagued them, among which are; lack of resources, poor government support, poor condition of service, lack of appropriate and adequate training and ill-equipped workforce. In addition, there are issues of police extortion and corruption, and other vices common among the police system, which contribute to their lack of efficiency.

Alemika (1999) posits that police corruption is a serious issue because they are expected to be morally sound as law-enforcement agents. If the police which were employed and catered for with the people's money to protect and detect crimes are themselves corrupt and also a party to crimes, then the society is at the mercy and grace of the criminals.

Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the assumptions of Situational Crime Prevention Theory of Ronald V. Clarke (1980). Situational crime prevention refers to how, in certain situations, adaptations can be made to prevent criminal acts. It involves looking at what crimes people commit, and where they commit them, when the crime was committed, how crime incidents occur and what can be done in that situation to prevent the crimes from happening. It seeks to reduce opportunities for specific categories of crime by increasing the associated risks and difficulties and reducing the rewards (Clarke, 1995). For situational crime prevention theory, crime is the result of an interaction between disposition and situation. Offenders choose to commit crime based on their perceptions of available opportunities. According to Clarke (1997), the situational crime prevention theory is drastically different from other criminological perspectives, different in the sense that it seeks to predict criminal behavior through focusing on proximal causes of crime in the settings where they occur rather than arresting and punishing offenders. It does not intend to prevent crime by addressing the

so called “root causes” of criminal offending such as social inequities, but rather does so through the reduction of crime opportunities.

Application of Situational Crime Prevention to the Study

The primary role of the security agencies is crime prevention. Situational crime prevention theory is considered very useful to this work because it is a framework that is capable of preventing or reducing opportunities to violent crimes. Violent crimes are perpetrated by hoodlums who have the opportunity. Therefore, violent crimes including armed robbery, cultism, rape, murder, kidnapping, arson, assassination, aggravated assault, among others took place as a result of the opportunities available to perpetrators of crime which can be prevented through surveillance, tip-off, beat patrols, community partnership and other crime prevention strategies. The availability of the law enforcement agents at strategic locations of the city or towns can alter immediate or situational factors in the environments where violent crime regularly occurs. With situational crime prevention, criminals and prospective criminals understand and become convinced that their actions are undesirable and are being monitored. It is incumbent upon the law enforcement agents to alter environments which host crime behaviour in order to make them less suitable for offending.

Methodology

The study was conducted in Akwa Ibom State where Uyo and Itu Local Government Areas were sampled. Descriptive survey research design and historical research design were adopted in the study. Descriptive survey research design aided the collection of primary data through structured and unstructured questionnaire and In-depth interview (IDI) guide. This research design was suitable because the researchers needed to meet with the respondents on face-to-face contact. Historical research design aided the collection of secondary data from online and newspaper publications.

A total of 400 respondents were selected to participate in the study using purposive sampling technique. Four hundred (400) copies of questionnaire were distributed to respondents to elicit information for the study and 395 were retrieved and same were used for statistical presentation and analysis. Population of the study constitutes security personnel, opinion leaders, traditional rulers, youths, women leaders, political class and ex-servicemen from 18 years and above, residing in Uyo and Itu Local Government Areas who have knowledge about incidence of violent crimes in their neighbourhoods and the role of security agencies.

In addition, In-depth interview (IDI) was conducted with selected security personnel and opinion leaders on the role of security agencies in curbing violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State. The IDI was conducted in English and Ibibio languages and a voice tape recorder was used. Voices of participants were tape recorded and at the same time note taking was done by one the authors. The tape recorded data gathered from IDI were transcribed in English. Quantitative data were descriptively presented and analyzed using frequency tables and simple percentages. Qualitative data gathered through in-depth interview were presented and analyzed using conversational analysis method. While, secondary data were presented to show the level of violent crimes in the state and the efforts of the security agencies in the fight against violent crimes.

Ethically, consent of the respondents was sort. They were informed about the purpose of the study and the need for their voices to be recorded. Identity of the authors was disclosed. Participants were given early information that participation in the study was voluntary. All sources of information were properly acknowledged using APA referencing style.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents (n = 395)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	210	53.16
Female	185	46.84
Total	395	100
Age (years)		
18-23	11	2.78
24-29	55	13.93
30-35	78	19.75
36-41	72	18.23
42-47	55	13.92
48-53	64	16.20
54 years and above	60	15.19
Total	395	100
Religion		
Christian	293	74.18
Islam	72	18.23
African Traditional Religion	2	0.51
Others	28	7.09
Total	395	100
Educational Attainment		
Primary	98	28.81
Secondary	159	40.25
University/Polytechnic/College of Education	138	34.94
Total	395	100
Security Personnel/ Community Leaders		
The Nigeria Police Force	50	12.66
Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps	50	12.66
Other law enforcement agents	50	12.66
Traditional rulers	50	12.66
Youth	50	12.66
Women Leaders	50	12.66
Political Class	50	12.66
Opinion Leaders	45	11.38
Total	395	100

Source: Field work (2019)

Table 1 show that males constitute 53.16% of the respondents while females constitute 46.84%. On age, 18-23 years are 2.78%, 24-29 years are 13.93%, 30-35 years are 19.75%, 36-41 years are 18.23%, 42-47 years are 13.92%, 48-53 years are 16.20% and 54 years and above are 15.19%. Therefore, the majority of respondents were within the age brackets of 30-35 years.

In terms of religion, 74.18% are Christians, 18.23% are Muslims, and adherents of African traditional religion are 0.51% while those of other religions not mentioned are 7.09%. Christians are the majority followed by Muslims.

On education, 28.81% attended primary school, 40.25% attended secondary school, while 34.94% attended university/polytechnic/college of education. This implies that majority in the population have gone to school.

On categories of respondents, the Nigeria Police Force are 12.66%, officers Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps are 12.66%, other Law Enforcement Agents are 12.66%, Traditional rulers 12.66%, youths are 12.66%, women leaders are 12.66%, 12.66% are political class while 11.38% are opinion leaders.

What are the Roles of Security Agencies in Curbing Violent Crimes?

In-depth interview with Mr. Emmanuel Udofia Udo, 42 years, opinion leader, residing at Ikot Mbonde Itam, Itu LGA

Question: How would you assess the role of security agencies in prevention of violent crimes in the state?

Response: The responsibility of security agencies is the prevention of crime occurrences, apprehension of offenders and deterring others from offending but frankly speaking, the law enforcement agents that we have today have not done enough to curb violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State.

Probe: Why do you think so?

Response: Our security agencies, especially, the police are poorly equipped, unreliable, corrupt and taking bribes to set culprits free. The police are timid, patrolling during periods of calm and disappearing during times of urban violence.

Question: Have you ever reported incidence of violent crime to the security agencies?

Response: Yes

Probe: Can you tell us the kind of violent crime you reported?

Response: Armed robbers invaded our community in the mid-night and we were alert

Probe: Which of the security agencies did you lay your complaint?

Response: I made a distress call to the police

Probe: Did you get any response from the police?

Response: They came after two hours and by that time the hoodlums had finished their operation and left the scene.

Probe: Did they tell you why they came late?

Response: They did not. Instead, they were asking us provoking questions

Probe: Please tell us one of the questions the Police asked you?

Response: Does it mean this community does not have community guards?

Probe: What was your response?

Response: We were disappointed in their operations. In fact, we have had similar experience and we know their delaying tactics. Our security agencies have failed in their responsibilities. I can say this anywhere.

In-depth interview with Chief Ubong Obot, 56 years, a community leader, residing at G-Line Ewet Housing Estate, Uyo

Question: Are you aware of the incidence of violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State?

Response: Yes, I am aware

Probe: What are the violent crimes known to you?

Response: I know about Cultism, armed robbery, kidnapping, rape, murder, assassination, political violence even hate speeches are forms of violent crimes. The perpetrators of these heinous crimes injured their victims in the course of their illegal operation.

Question: In your opinion, what are the roles of security agencies in curbing violent crimes?

Response: To an average Nigerian citizen, police duties are simply to apprehend law breakers and prevent any form of crimes, maintain law and order and protect lives and property. Those are things I see them doing, although there lapses anyway...

Probe: How do the security agents perform these functions?

Response: For the police, the law empowers them to stop, question, detain, and arrest people who violate the law. They also investigate crimes, collect and preserve evidence for criminal trial.

Probe: Please tell us the strategies they used in combating violent crimes?

Response: For me, I know that police do patrol with their vehicles to detect and deter crime offenders; they also do stop and search by positioning their officers at check points, also they provides emergency contacts to the public for distress calls and many others.

Probe: Do you think these strategies mentioned are effective?

Response: I cannot say yes or no. Criminal activities are everywhere; we cannot sleep with our two eyes closed. Something needs to be done to quell these violent crimes.

Probe: What do you think are the causes of violent crimes?

Response: I would say, it is unemployment, poverty, and the cost of living is high, poor parental upbringing, peer group influence, inefficiency of the security personnel, among others.

Probe: What do you think should be done to curb violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State?

Response: Government should create job opportunities for the teeming youths. The high cost of living should be reduced through massive agriculture. Government should embark on poverty alleviations programmes. Finally, the law enforcement agencies should be properly equipped and supervised. Members of the public should support the police by giving them information that could help the police to arrest those who have violated the law.

In-depth interview with Mr. Ndianabasi Essien Tom, 38 years, staff of Akwa Ibom State Judiciary, residing at Nung Uyio Idoro, Uyo

Question: Do you think the security agencies have any role to play in curbing violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State?

Response: Yes

Probe: What are the roles?

Response: Security agents are empowered to prevent social disorder. This they do by deploying their personnel to patrol strategic roads, quarters and other parts of towns and cities to maintain law and order. Security agency like the police utilizes various crime prevention tactics like stake-outs, decoys and night patrols. Ordinary private citizen is relied upon information to enable the police or other law enforcement agents go to scenes of crime to investigate and make arrest where necessary. It is their duty to investigate most cases of alleged criminal behaviours and make appropriate recommendations for trial in the court of law. It is unfortunate that our security personnel are unable to perform their assigned duties due to some internal issues in the system.

Probe: What are the internal issues in the system?

Response: It is corruption, poor funding, and manpower shortage, lack of training and retraining of personnel, illiteracy and lack of transparency in recruitment process, to mention but few.

From the above, the primary duty of the security agencies is the prevention of crime. Opinion reveals that weakness of police response to distress calls and the consequent impunity of offenders create a climate of fear and insecurity in the state. Many citizens have lost confidence in Nigeria police and other security agencies due to high incidence of crime and resorted to a life of self-help.

How effective are the Strategies Adopted by Security Agencies in Curbing Violent Crimes in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 2: Frequency distribution of respondents according to the effectiveness of strategies adopted by security agencies in curbing violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Ineffective	150	37.97
Very Ineffective	97	24.56
Undecided	5	1.27
Effective	91	23.04
Very Effective	52	13.16
Total	395	100

Source: Field work (2019)

Table 2 indicates that 37.97% are of the opinion that strategies adopted by security agencies in curbing violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State are ineffective, 24.56% says that it is very ineffective, 1.27% are undecided, 23.04% says that the strategies adopted by security agencies in curbing violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State are effective and 13.16% says very effective. This implies that majority of respondents are of the opinion that the strategies adopted by security agencies in curbing violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State are not effective owing to increase in violent crimes across the state. The citizens are not safe in their homes, work places, and while in transit. The security agencies need to go back to the drawing table and re-strategize on how fight violent crime in the state to a halt.

In-depth interview with Inspector Okon Akpan Uko (rtd), 68 years old, residing at Nkim Itam, Itu Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State

Question: Do you think the strategies adopted by security agencies are enough to curb violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State?

Response: Not really

Probe: what do you mean?

Response: Security agencies have their strategies of preventing crime occurrences. I am a retired Police Officer; I have served in the Nigeria Police Force for 35 years before my retirement. The importance of law and order in the society cannot be overemphasized and the place of law enforcement in the scheme of things remains paramount. For instance, the Nigeria Police have used stop and search, tip-off, beat patrols and monitoring, check-points, static guards and partnership with community leaders in order to prevent crime and maintain law and order but how effective are these strategies is the question.

Probe: Are you saying that the strategies are ineffective?

Response: Let me quickly say that some of these strategies are no longer effective.

Probe: How Sir?

Response: The incidence and intensity of violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State have been in the increase, and the way of combating the rising wave is very challenging. Crimes are committed everywhere in the state and little is done by our security agencies to prevent criminal activities. Citizens have lost hope

Probe: What are these challenges?

Response: Security personnel are suffering. Their salaries are meager compared to the tedious jobs, bribery and corruption have ravaged the system, people have become enemies to security personnel, funding is totally poor and intelligence is becoming weaker. Could you imagine that I am yet to receive my retirement benefits after five (5) years? This is uncalled for.

Findings reveal that the general perception of the strategies adopted by security agencies in curbing violent crime in Akwa Ibom State was not encouraging. Only 32.2 percent of all the respondents felt that the strategies adopted by security agencies in curbing violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State were considered effective. Majority were saying it is ineffective.

What constitute hindrances to Fighting Violent Crimes among Security Agencies in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 3: Hindrances of the security agencies in curbing violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Lack of adequate funds	54	13.67
Inadequate training	44	11.14
ill-equipped workforce	88	22.28
Bribery and Corruption	63	15.95
Poor welfare packages	60	15.19
Poor public perception	56	14.18
Poor recruitment process	30	7.59
Total	395	100

Source: Field work (2019)

Table 3 shows the hindrances of the security agencies in the course of performing their duties in relation to violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State; 13.67% are of the opinion that lack of adequate funds is one of the challenges, 11.14% said that it is inadequate training, 22.28% are of the opinion that it is ill-equipped workforce, 15.95% said that it is bribery and corruption, 15.19% said it is poor welfare packages, 14.18% said that it is poor recruitment process, and 37.59% attributes it to poor recruitment process.

In-depth interview with Asp Akahalu Ogbonaya of the State Investigation Department, Ikot Akpan Abia, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

Question: How long have worked with the Nigeria Police Force?

Response: 26 years

Question: Do you think there are militating factors against curbing violent crimes by security agencies?

Response: Yes

Probe: How do you mean?

Response: Despite the enormous responsibilities entrusted on the police in Nigeria, the Nigeria Police Force is incompetent and incapable of combating and controlling crimes. I am saying this as an insider.

Probe: Why did you say so?

Response: I am saying this because, the most serious and problematic violent crimes, especially, armed robbery, murder, assassinations, cultism, rape, etc. have been reported on a daily basis and it is spreading like wild fire and the law enforcement agents cannot prevent them from happening. It is a pity!

Probe: What do you think should be the reason?

Response: The reasons are consequences of militating factors including lack of adequate operational equipment (communication equipment, logistic vehicles, weapons, residential accommodations, etc), inadequate training and re-orientation of law enforcement operatives charged with combating crime, gross lack of support from the public. This is manifested either due to lack of security consciousness or lack of trust in the police personnel by the citizenry. There are bad elements in the system coupled with the fact that police are not well paid and this has been the reason most security personnel enriched themselves through corruption.

Findings reveal that security agencies in Akwa Ibom State are facing a lot of challenges including ill-equipped workforce, poor welfare packages, corruption, lack of trust and public support, etc. These have brought a serious setback to the entire system.

What is the level and trend of violent crimes in Akwa Ibom State?

Secondary data reveals thus:

Ukpong (2020) reported the increase in armed robbery attacks in Uyo, the Akwa Ibom capital, prompting the governor, Mr Udom Emmanuel to hold an emergency Security Council meeting. He added that shops and offices were hurriedly closed in Uyo before 8 p.m. and the streets deserted because of the fear of armed robbers. He also added that the Police Spokesperson in the state, Odiko MacDon, disclosed that 40 armed robbery suspects have been arrested in the state.

Bassey (2020) reported that the Akwa Ibom State Commissioner of Police, Imohimi Edgal during a town hall meeting/security summit held in Uyo confirmed the arrest of 171 suspected criminals and rescued 19 kidnapped persons within the months of December 2019 and February 2020. Imohimi Edgal added that 14 different types of firearms and 25 types of ammunition were recovered from the hoodlums, 38 different types of exhibits in police custody. A total of 94 persons have been charged to court, while cases still under investigation remain at 77. The police could not be everywhere as a result of shortfall in manpower, encouraged communities to take up strategic policing by setting up vigilante groups and deepening police participation. Imohimi Edgal also said that parents have failed in the duties of training their children, lamenting that it showed we were building a society of cultism and called on all to join hands to stop the menace.

Onyedinefu (2020) and the Nigerian Pulse Editorial (2020) reported that on 14th June, 2020, the Akwa Ibom State Police Command arrested a 60-year-old Village Head of Ikot Inyang in Ibesikpo Asutan Local Government Area, Etteidung Stephen Uyoe, for allegedly defiling an 11-year-old girl. The Police Public Relations Officer, Mr. Fredrick Nnudam, who disclosed this in Uyo, said the police also arrested one Pastor Victor Victor David in Etim Ekpo Local Government Area for defiling an 8-year-old girl. On May 28, 2020, police arrested a 30-year-old man identified as Okon Henry, a native of Mbokpueyokan Village, Urue-Offong Oruko Local Government Area for forcefully raping his 17-year-old niece. On 13th June, 2020, operatives of 'C' Division arrested one Solomon Okon and Becky Umoretuk who conspired and lured a 26-year-old lady to their house and unlawfully assaulted her with fist blow and machet, and in the process, Solomon Okon forcefully had unlawful carnal knowledge of the victim.

Premium Times Editorial (2020) reported that the Police Public Relations Officer (PPRO), Odiko Macdon, disclosed in a statement issued in Uyo that based on intelligence information the tactical team of the command stormed criminal hideouts on December 10, 2020 and arrested 40 persons suspected to be involved in armed robbery and cultism activities within Uyo Metropolis with two locally-made pistols, five cutlasses, a bag of substance suspected to be Indian Hemp were among the exhibits recovered.

Onuegbu (2019) reported that Akwa Ibom State Government through the Commissioner for Agriculture and Women Affairs, Dr. Glory Edet during a press briefing on the commemoration of 16 days of activism for the elimination of violence against women said that since October 4, 2018,

over 180 cases have been received and over 18 culprits have been successfully prosecuted especially cases of defilement and rape.

Odey (2019) reported that a tricycle operator, one Mr. Edet Edem was taken to police custody for allegedly defiling a 10-year-old girl (name withheld) in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Edem, 27 years old, who hails from Oku Iboku in Itu Local Government Area of the state, was apprehended for allegedly committing the crime by youths of Use Offot village, where he rented an apartment. It was gathered that the tricycle operator, after committing the crime, took the girl to Use Offot market square and dumped her there while she was bleeding. The girl was later rescued by a passerby, Mariam Daniels, who rushed her to Anua Hospital, along Nwaniba in Uyo for medical treatment. Mariam Daniels, a member of a non-governmental organization, Journalists Alliance Against Gender-Based Violence said; "I was moved by the victim's pitiable state after noticing that the girl was lying helplessly in the market square. I took the girl to the suspect's residence and when I arrived there, I saw a pool of blood in the suspect's apartment. The suspect's door was locked and there was no indication that he was within the neighbourhood" (Odey, 2019).

Duru (2017) reported that on the 12th December, 2017 following a distress call, a gang of six cultists armed with machetes and axe were arrested at Itam, Uyo after robbing two female victims of their phones and purse containing some amount of money. Also reported was that, on the 9th December, 2017 Police operatives acting on information busted a group of suspected cultists who converged at Isangedighi Lane, Oron for secret meeting and arrested one Ernest Etim Bassey (male) of No. 4 Eyo-Abasi Estate, Oron and 6 other members of his gang. One locally made pistol and photograph of suspect with other group members were recovered. On 10th December, 2017 following a credible intelligence, Police operatives raided another cult den at Abak town. Twelve (12) suspects were arrested and the following items were recovered; military belts, binoculars, Navy beret. The suspects confessed to be members of a secret cult engaged in various crimes in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District and its environs. Duru (2017) also reported that on 11th December, 2017 at about 01:15hrs in Oruk Anam Local Government Area Police arrested one Uyoattah Umoh Jacob (male), a 100 level student of Akwa Ibom State University (Ata Obio Akpa Campus) for cultism. One locally made single barrel gun was recovered from him.

In-depth interview with Mr. Agbagwa Kingsley Ogedirihenile, 43 years old, residing at Mbak Atai, Oron Road, Uyo

Question: How long have stayed in Akwa Ibom State?

Response: I have stayed in Uyo for more than five (5) years now

Question: What would you say about the situation of violent crimes in the state?

Response: The entire Uyo Metropolis that I know has been overridden by the activities of cultism and other criminal activities.

Probe: How do you mean?

Response: I know this to be true for a very long time. Their faces might look like responsible people, but you will be surprised by their actions. They are everywhere.

Probe: Why did you say so?

Response: I can tell you how many times I have encountered cultists and how I lost my belongings and the injuries I sustained in the course of struggling with the hoodlums.

Probe: Please can you tell us what happened to you?

Response: It is a long story. I was robbed for two consecutive times at my residence and valuables were catered away by armed robbers. The armed robbers were six (6) in number all with guns and other weapons. One of my family members was raped in the process. I took her to the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital and I spent a lot of money before she could recover. In another occasion, I was robbed by suspected cult members when I was returning from work, although, it was a bit late.

Probe: Did you report it to the law enforcement agents?

Response: I did not

Probe: Why?

Response: I didn't want to spend my resources in addition to what I have already lost.

In-depth interview with Csp Francis Erhabor, the Divisional Police Officer (Dpo), D Division Itam, Itu Lga

Question: What is the security situation in your area of jurisdiction?

Response: Let me quickly tell you that it is a serious challenge nowadays and the police are worried over this unfortunate situation.

Probe: How do you mean Sir?

Response: Cultism is commonly reported. Cultists have terrorized the society and their atrocities are enamous. For cultists, most times they found out that police are now aware of their usual modus operandi. Before now they made use of uncompleted buildings and schools that have no parameter fence. In a way to advance their course, they resorted to engaging or use tricycles to take them to interior places outside the outskirts of town. The last one we had was at Ikot Ebom Ikono area where tricycles were used to aid close to thirty persons and they were moving in batches. In a sense too, tricycles have also been used in the advancement of cultism because it is the easiest means of city transportation since motorcycles are not allowed access to the city. So, tricycles could serve in the place of motorcycles to convey cultists to where they converge to carry out their ungodly meetings and attacks.

Probe: Do you have any report of people using tricycles to rob unsuspected members of the public?

Response: Yes

Probe: Please can you explain?

Response: We have some cases in my jurisdiction where we were able to apprehend some hoodlums who used the guise of being tricycle riders to rob their victims. For them, it is a quicker way of making returns to the owners of the tricycles who might not be privileged to know what the riders use or engages the tricycle for. We had a situation where a tricycle rider was actually apprehended based on a tip off. The suspect was using the tricycle to assist vandals of electric poles and other electronic gadgets like street lights and transformer. He has been doing it for a very long time. His duty was to go and convey those things to a particular destination and he was paid heavily for it. We also had some cases where some people lodged in a Hotel not far from my end, precisely along Nelson Mandela Road, Uyo. They were three and what they did was that they rob victims and sometimes they took victims to ATM under gun point and robbed them of their hard earned money with the aid of tricycle. In fact, recently at Ikot Ambang in Ibiono Ibom Local Government Area, very close to us, three people in a tricycle conveyed a woman and robbed the woman of her money and pushed the woman out of Keke while on motion. A Tipper driver who was behind the tricycle saw what happen before him and ran after the tricycle and hit them intentionally so that at least that will help apprehend the suspects and the youths in the area who saw what was going on pursued the suspects and a jungle justice was carried out.

Results show that the level and trend of violent crime in Akwa Ibom State have increased rapidly, needs urgent attention. Majority of respondents were of the opinion that the level and trend of violent crimes in the state have increased in intensity making the people to live in fear of insecurity.

Discussion of Findings

The Roles of Security Agencies in Curbing Violent Crimes

Findings revealed that security agencies in Akwa Ibom State have tried their best in preventing crime occurrences but crime investigations are in the increase, making the public to have a picture that our security personnel are not proactive in their operations. One should understand that the primary responsibility of any security agency is the prevention of crime. The law enforcement powers of the Nigeria Police Force are derived from the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999). It is the foremost agency recognized by law with the constitutional authority to maintain law and order, prevent and control crime and provide security and protection not only for the lives of Nigerians and also to those who reside in Nigeria and their property. In fact, the duties of the police are defined in section 4 of the Police Act, as “the prevention and detection of crime, the apprehension of offenders, the preservation of law and order, the protection of property and the due enforcement of all laws and regulations with which they are directly charged”. According to the Police regulations of 1968, the Force Intelligence and Investigation Bureau (FIIB) have as its first primary responsibility, the prevention of crime and not the investigation of crime as it is popularly believed. Criminal investigation according Suleiman (1996) forms only “its secondary responsibility, which was evolved to cover lapses in its primary preventive function”. Vigilant security personnel deter criminals who have the intention of committing a crime(s).

Effectiveness of the Strategies Adopted by Security Agencies in Curbing Violent Crimes

Findings revealed that indeed, stop and search at strategic locations, tip-off from informants, day and night patrols, aggressive anti-crime patrols, road block/check points, imposition of curfews in certain strategic and crime infested parts of cities and towns, arrest and detention of people who violate the law are all strategies considered to be very effective in deterring criminals but here in Akwa Ibom State, these strategies have yielded little result as the rate of violent crimes increases. Most Nigerians do not perceive the NPF as an effective law enforcement body, and have little faith in the criminal justice system. A call to police for assistance may result in the solicitation of bribes. Criminal groups do not fear arrest or prosecution for their activities. Local police and neighborhood associations generally do not deter or disrupt crimes, and seldom apprehend or detain suspects. This study is supported by Morris and Heal (1981) who came to a conclusion that police have little effect on the level of crime. Hough and Clarke (1980) also concluded that it is inappropriate to use the concept of effectiveness in assessing police work. If correct, these conclusions have implications for the management of the police and for the content of future research programmes. Karn (2013) cited in Etuk (2018) suggested that these strategies are relatively ineffective in reducing crime and detecting offenders.

Hindrances to Curbing Violent Crimes among Security Agencies in Akwa Ibom State

Findings show that security agencies in Akwa Ibom State have faced with a lot of challenges in curbing violent crimes. These challenges include lack of adequate operational equipment (communication equipment, logistic vehicles, weapons, residential accommodations, etc), inadequate training and re-orientation of law enforcement operatives charged with combating crime, gross lack of support from the public, illiteracy, corruption, poor recruitment process, among others. Despite a visible police presence in large cities, police response is variable. Security agencies usually respond slowly or not at all, and provide minimal investigative support to victims. The Rapid Response Squad’s policing capacity and emergency response capabilities continue to grow, but remain in a nascent state. A serious lack of resources (e.g. communications equipment, vehicles,

skilled leadership, and training) continues to undermine the effectiveness of the Nigeria Police Force (NPF).

Usually, victims must maintain close contact with local police to move an investigation forward. Crime laboratories and facilities to process evidence are rare. This finding is supported by Chinwokwu (2018) who said that some crimes are beyond the scope and jurisdiction of public law enforcement agencies, because they do not have the sufficient resources, expertise and technological know-how to track sophisticated criminals. Also, Onovo (2005) posits that the barriers that reduce the capacity of agencies to share criminal intelligence include the following: lack of a national process for generating and sharing intelligence, etc.

The Level and Trend of Violent Crimes in Akwa Ibom State

Findings show that incidence of violent crimes are highly concentrated in Akwa Ibom State. Respondents' experiences of violent crimes were mainly cultism, armed robbery, rape, murder, the use of firearms, assassinations and kidnapping for ransom. The increasing rate of violent crimes in the state is a signal to the security agencies to be proactive and to know that more effort needs to be put in place in order to put the hoodlums on check. There are clashes between cult groups in many communities, killings in the name of politics, armed robbery in the night and day time; rape at gun points, proliferation of arms and cases of shootings, fear dominates every part of the state because of insecurity. There is no doubt whatsoever that the use of firearms plays a very central role in the commission of crime. The relationship between firearms and crime is not surprising. During crackdowns on secrete cult members, it happens that a large amount of firearms and other sophisticated weapons are being recovered from them, many of whom double as armed robbers and hired assassins. The police also display daily, the weapons seized from criminal groups. Kidnapping for ransom is prevalent throughout Nigeria. Victims often come from the Nigerian Diaspora when they return home from abroad for either a holiday or a specific reason (death in the family/wedding); criminals target them due to their perceived affluence.

However, kidnappers take multiple expatriates each year. Kidnappers frequently target road travelers, and abduct victims from their residences or other frequented locations. Security escorts and guards do not deter all kidnappers. Often, the victim's family pays a ransom and the kidnappers returned the victim unharmed. Rape remains a serious problem. There is no comprehensive national law for combating violence against women. Rape is a crime in Nigeria, but sentences for persons convicted of rape and sexual assault are inconsistent and often minor. Multiple armed criminal elements exist throughout Nigeria, ranging from low-level to organized syndicates. Cultist or gang violence, which often erupts in supremacy battles between various groups, is a concern. Home invasions remain a serious threat, with armed robbers even targeting guarded compounds. Perpetrators have scaled perimeter walls, followed residents/visitors, and/or subdued guards to gain entry.

The survey found that people have refused to report their experiences of criminal victimization to the security agencies; instead, they do so with their family members or they may decide not to report to anyone at all. This finding is supported by work of Ukoji and Okolie-Osemene (2016) who posits that cult related activities abound in the nooks and crannies of our society especially in institutions of learning. Wilson (1983) concluded that it is the police that is saddled with the responsibility to prevent social disorder, and by social disorder, is meant behaviour that either disturbs or threatens to disturb the public peace or that involves face-to-face conflict among two or more persons. Wilson (1983) further maintained that it is important that the police rather than some other professionals respond to such problems because they may result in violence.

Conclusion

The study investigated the role of security agencies in curbing violent crimes in Nigeria using Akwa Ibom State as a case study. Findings in the study have provided significant answers to

the research questions raised in the course of the study. The role of security agencies in the prevention of violent crimes cannot be overemphasized in any society that is yearning for sustainable development. It can be established from the survey, the overall picture produced by the survey findings is that violent crimes are in the increase in Akwa Ibom State and security agencies are finding it difficult to curb its spread. Since crime is one of the human security problems confronting humanity across the world, effort must be made to reduce crime, especially violent crimes.

Recommendations

- i. Every community should embrace and adopt community watch as a crime prevention strategy. Community watch is a crime prevention method that involves citizens working with each other and with law enforcement agencies to reduce crime and victimization in their communities. The goal of community watch is to make criminals aware that every move is being watched and will be reported to the police. It involves citizens protecting themselves and their property by using common sense crime prevention practices; neighbours getting to know each other, watching out for each other and acting on or reporting suspicious activities; citizens working with groups, community leaders, and, more importantly, law enforcement agencies to make entire communities safe and free from hoodlums.
- ii. Preventing crime is preferable to dealing with crime after it has occurred. Therefore, security personnel should be able to deter, eliminate or minimize criminal opportunities whenever possible and encourage citizens to report suspicious behaviours which are considered inimical to public order and as well protect themselves and their property and others in the neighbourhoods.
- iii. Cooperation and partnerships between the security agencies and citizens are necessary. The police should operate in a way that the citizen will have confidence in them. Citizens with vital information about crimes sometimes fail to contact the police because they fear retaliation or they do not want to appear in court. The result is that many criminals are still walking our streets and committing other crimes. Therefore, every criminal activity should be reported immediately to the police. Once a criminal is successfully taken off the streets, he is no longer a threat to you, your children and your business.
- iv. There is need for government at all levels to ensure a permanent place for crime prevention in their structures and programmes. The role of the government is to provide leadership, coordination, and adequate funding and resources. How can this role be played by national, regional or local governments? The recommendations include the establishment of:
 - ✓ A permanent central authority
 - ✓ A crime prevention plan with clear priorities and targets
 - ✓ Coordination and partnerships between government agencies and civil society
 - ✓ Public education and communication
 - ✓ Sustainability and accountability of programmes
 - ✓ Training and capacity-building for government and other bodies
- V. Human and technical resources and their proper management are important to improving security. The improved resource base and inter-agency cooperation; physical planning; and environmental and social policies could reduce the level and trend of violent crimes in the country.

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